

Re-coding Seis8s: A Web Audio Remix of a Latin Music Live Coding Language

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ABSTRACT

Seis8s (<https://seis8s.org>) is a Spanish-inflected, web-based live coding environment designed to foreground Latin electronic dance music traditions, especially cumbia. Building on earlier iterations[7, 8], this paper presents a major reimplementa-tion using Vue.js[17], Tone.js[11], Tonal.js[1], and Scalable Vector Graphics (SVG). The new version introduces a symbolic syntax that integrates pitch and rhythm in a single timeline, adds inline repetition shortcuts, and uses Unicode musical symbols for greater clarity and expressiveness. The interface departs from minimalist UI norms by adopting a visual identity inspired by Peruvian Chicha poster art, realized through vibrant colors, irregular type-faces, and SVG-based interaction. User feedback from workshops and a live performance suggests that these changes make Seis8s both more engaging for musicians and more approachable for non-coders.

1. INTRODUCTION

Seis8s is a web-based environment designed to foreground Latin electronic dance music traditions, especially cumbia music, through real-time programming of Spanish commands that produce rhythmic and melodic patterns. Cumbia is a folkloric music and dance tradition originating from Colombia’s Caribbean coast, characterized by syncopated rhythms, call-and-response structures, and a fusion of Indigenous, African, and European influences.

Originally prototyped in 2023 as part of my PhD dissertation entitled *Culturally situated programming platforms: seis8s, a live-coding language for electronic Latin dance music*[14], Seis8s was designed following live coding’s ethos, where both performer and audience engage not just with the sound but with the code projected in real time[5].

In addition to this, the cultural and musical rationale of Seis8 is aimed at supporting Latin electronic traditions in creative coding spaces by: speculating the look and feel of a computer-music language grounded in Spanish, and addressing a Hispanophone imagined community of users with shared cultural, political, economic, historical and technological traits[8].

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Seis8s is freely available at <https://seis8s.org>, with source publicly available on GitHub at <https://github.com/luisnavarrodelangel/seis8s-exe>. Released under the MIT License, it can be reused, modified, and redistributed with minimal restrictions, supporting creative exploration and collaborative development.

1.1 Limitations of the First Seis8s

While the original Seis8s provided a proof of concept, it exposed several friction points that motivated the reimplementation I discuss in this paper. First, its technological stack—built using Reflex-FRP, a Haskell framework—made even minor interface tweaks slow and difficult to iterate. Secondly, musical expressions required melodies and rhythms to be encoded as separate lists, which made writing and reading code cumbersome, particularly in improvisational contexts. Finally, the original interface, while functional, lacked a visual identity that reflected the vibrancy of the musical cumbia traditions it aimed to represent.

Recognizing these limitations, the new iteration of Seis8s was reimplemented using a combination of Vue.js, Tone.js, and Tonal.js, which offer greater flexibility and rapid iteration. Melody and rhythm now coexist within a single symbolic timeline to enhance immediacy and expressiveness, and the interface was redesigned with a visual identity inspired by Peruvian Chicha street posters using bright colors, jagged fonts, and energetic layouts.

2. TECHNICAL RE-IMPLEMENTATION

The redevelopment of Seis8s was motivated by three main goals: increasing development flexibility, improving the expressiveness of the language, and enhancing the visual identity of the interface.

2.1 Increasing Development Flexibility: From Haskell to a JavaScript Ecosystem

The decision to move Seis8s from its original Haskell-based implementation to a JavaScript ecosystem was driven by a combination of developer experience, performance demands, and the need for broader accessibility. While Haskell and Reflex-FRP provided a robust, type-safe environment that shaped many early ideas about musical structure and syntax validation in Seis8s, they also introduced practical barriers to experimentation and iteration.

In Reflex-FRP, even minor changes to Seis8s’ codebase required a full recompilation. As Seis8s grew in complexity, these compile times increased significantly, sometimes

taking between thirty seconds and two minutes. This delay broke the immediacy of my creative development process, especially when testing speculative features or resolving minor bugs.

Furthermore, the Haskell/Reflex-FRP stack presented a steep learning curve for potential collaborators. Installing the right dependencies, understanding functional reactive programming, and modifying the interface all required specialized knowledge. I realized that if Seis8s were to become a more shareable, remixable, or pedagogical tool, its technical foundation needed to be more accessible.

In response, I chose to rebuild Seis8s in Vue.js, a lightweight JavaScript framework that supports simple beginnings while allowing for scalable architecture. Vue’s Options API and CDN-based setup enabled me to start prototyping quickly without complex tooling.

2.1.1 A New Sonic Foundation

On the audio side, the original version of Seis8s relied on WebDirt, a JavaScript audio library created for the Estuary live coding platform[15]. Estuary, built with Reflex-FRP, used the MiniTidal language—a simplified form of Tidal-Cycles[12]. Although WebDirt served as a valuable starting point, it was tightly coupled with TidalCycles idioms and had minimal documentation.

In contrast, switching to Tone.js offered a robust and flexible audio sampling and scheduling library with a growing community and detailed documentation. Tone.js made it easier for me to handle low-latency playback, tempo control, sample triggering, and timing grids, allowing musical precision and native browser compatibility.

Furthermore, Seis8s now integrates Tonal.js, a JavaScript library for music theory. This allowed me to eliminate much of the hardcoded logic around scales, degrees, and note conversion that I had previously written by hand in Haskell and made compatible with WebDirt’s logic. Tonal.js provides clean abstractions for building chords, mapping pitch classes, and managing key relationships, helping me reduce code complexity and improve consistency across musical layers.

2.2 Improving Expressiveness: Unified Symbolic Timeline for Rhythm and Melody

The most significant musical advancement in the new version of Seis8s is the ability to express both rhythm and melody within a single symbolic timeline. Rather than separating note values and rhythmic durations into two lists—as was required in earlier versions—the new syntax allows performers to write musically coherent phrases that blend these elements visually and semantically.

```
bajo tumbao ♩/1 ♩/3 ♩/5
```

Figure 1: A Seis8s pattern using the new unified symbolic timeline, combining rhythm (half and quarter notes) and pitch symbols into a single coherent sequence for the bass (bajo) instrument.

Rhythmically, the syntax borrows from practical music notation, including jazz lead sheets and rhythmic charts used by drummers. Harmonically, it blends note symbols with chord degrees, adapting ideas from the Nashville Number System, a popular shorthand for expressing scale degrees

```
tumbao [1a 3a 5a] [1 3 4] $ bajo;
```

Figure 2: A Seis8s pattern demonstrating the original list-based syntax, where pitch (left list) and rhythm (right list) are encoded separately for a bass (bajo) instrument.

(e.g., 3, 5) within harmonic contexts.

2.2.1 Timeline Parsing and Instrument Sequencing

From a technical perspective, this new syntax is parsed with a custom grammar written in Peggy.js[16], implementing a parsing expression grammar[9] for the web. It recognizes compound expressions like those shown above as rhythm–pitch pairs, which are then transformed into lists of JavaScript objects with explicit note(or chord degree), duration, and timing, as shown below.

```
{time: '0:0:0', note: 1, duration: '2n'},
{time: '0:2:0', note: 3, duration: '4n'},
{time: '0:3:0', note: 5, duration: '4n'}
```

Figure 3: Example of three parsed rhythm–pitch pairs from the bajo tumbao pattern (♩/1, ♩/3, ♩/5), represented as JavaScript objects with explicit fields for chord degree, duration, and timing.

Seis8s computes time values through incremental beat arithmetic and represents events in the time, value format required by Tone.js’s Part class, enabling seamless scheduling of multiple instruments (e.g., bajo, guiro, teclado) on a shared timeline with few extra transformation steps.

```
tempo 100
armonia [Cmaj | Dm]
teclado acompañamiento ♩ ♩ ♩
bajo tumbao ♩/1 ♩/3 ♩/5
bombo ritmo ♩ ♩ ♩
guiro ritmo ♩ ♩ ♩
```

Figure 4: A sample code of Seis8s including keyboard (teclado), bass guitar (bajo), bombo (kick drum), and scraper (guiro) as well as tempo and harmony (armonia)

2.2.2 Unicode Notation and Live Coding Commands

To facilitate live coding performance, Seis8s allows users to enter musical notes and rests using simple textual commands that are automatically replaced with corresponding musical symbols. For example, entering 4n in the editor is immediately replaced with a quarter note symbol (♩), while 8n produces an eighth note (♪). Similarly, rests are entered using commands such as 4s for a quarter rest (♩), 8s for an eighth rest, and so on.

This approach avoids the need for performers to type or memorize Unicode symbols directly, allowing them to focus on musical structure and improvisation. At the time of writing, a complete list of commands and their corresponding symbols is available in the Seis8s documentation at <https://seis8s.org/docs>.

A challenge emerged around note symbol rendering, since musical Unicode characters are not reliably displayed across all systems or browsers. To address this, I modified the

Galada font (a decorative Google font) used in Seis8s by including these symbols directly into the font, ensuring that they render consistently across platforms, including mobile devices.

2.2.3 Pattern Repetition Shortcuts

Another limitation of the previous version of Seis8s was the lack of a built-in repetition mechanism. Performers had to write out each bar or phrase explicitly, which could quickly produce very long lists of pitches and rhythms, especially when composing melodic lines. The bars were separated by commas, which could make reading patterns difficult.

The new syntax introduces two key improvements: inline repetition of measures using the colons (: ... :) to mark repeated sections, and separation of measures with a pipe symbol (|), which is visually closer to standard musical notation. These changes allow for more concise, readable patterns while maintaining rhythmic consistency. Performers can now iterate rapidly during live coding performances without losing track of the musical structure.

```
bajo tumbao [ ♩/1 ♩/3 ♩/5 | : ♩/1 ♩/3 ♩/5 ♩/5:]
```

Figure 5: Example of inline repetition in Seis8s. The bass pattern (bajo tumbao) defines two measures: the first contains half and quarter notes, while the second contains half, quarter, and eighth notes. The second measure, enclosed by : :, is repeated without rewriting the sequence.

```
tumbao [1a 3a 5a, 1a 3a 5a 5a, 1a 3a 5a 5a] [1 3 4, 1 3 4 4.5 , 1 3 4 4.5] $ bajo;
```

Figure 6: How the previous version of Seis8s required explicit repetition: the bass pattern (bajo) repeats pitch and rhythm lists for each measure, leading to long and cumbersome sequences without a concise repetition mechanism.

2.3 Enhancing The Visual Interface Through Peruvian Chicha Aesthetics

Another significant shifts in the redesign of Seis8s was visual, where the interface no longer aims for minimalist clarity or conformity with design system standards. Instead, it draws inspiration from the vivid and chaotic energy of Peruvian Chicha poster art, which is the "Peruvian Kitsch aesthetic ... born in the 1980s"[2] that deliberately breaks from modernist design principles, layering bold colors, irregular letterforms, and multiple fonts in ways that feel exuberant and unruly[6].

Figure 7: A screenshot of Seis8s old interface

Figure 8: A screenshot of Seis8s new interface

While I am originally from Mexico, I have long been captivated by Chicha culture and its expressive typography, often associated with Peruvian cumbia and street-level visual communication. Similar artistic practices exist in Mexico, such as the rotulismo style used to paint local business signs and street food menus [10].

The color scheme was derived from the work of Chicha artist Jefferson Huamán, particularly a poster featured on Movimientos.org[13], which mixes saturated green, orange, and purple tones in asymmetric, high-contrast layouts.

2.3.1 Breaking UI Norms through Chicha Art

By embracing aesthetic choices that traditional interface design might consider mistakes—vibrant, almost fluorescent color palettes, mixed typefaces, and a layout that prioritizes energy over order—the new Seis8s interface intentionally resists sterile user interface norms such as Apple’s Human Interface Guidelines[4] or Google’s Material Design system[3], where hierarchy, harmony, and consistency are central values.

Instead of striving for balance and legibility at all costs, the Chicha-inspired approach foregrounds visual intensity and rhythmic disruption, aiming to provoke attention rather than soothe it. In this way, the interface becomes not just a neutral container for musical code, but an expressive surface that amplifies the exuberant cultural references of the performance itself.

2.3.2 Design workflow and technical pipeline

The design process began in Figma, where I composed the interface as a flat graphic using SVGs. Once exported, the SVG file was imported into the Vue.js framework and transformed into an interactive layer—allowing users to click on buttons, launch sound events, or interact with timeline controls directly on top of the artwork.

The use of SVG as an interface foundation emerged not only from aesthetic goals, but also from pedagogical insight. While teaching a course on design and code in 2023, I came to appreciate SVG’s expressive power which allows to draw complex layouts, then render them in the browser exactly as envisioned, without having to deconstruct every visual into CSS grids, box models, or flex alignment rules. This made SVG an appealing medium for expressing the visual culture of Chicha art, where irregular forms and layered typography resist standard layout logic.

Despite its potential, SVG is often dismissed in web development circles due to perceived limitations in accessibility. Unlike HTML, which carries built-in semantic structure and roles, SVGs are often treated as decorative or non-interactive, especially when exported as static graphics. However, these limitations are not inherent to the format. SVG accessibility can be improved using several strategies—such as adding `<title>` and `<desc>` tags for screen readers; defining `role="img"` and `aria-labelledby` attributes; structuring SVGs with `<g>` (group) tags to provide semantic grouping; and ensuring keyboard focus and navigability through event listeners and `tabindex`.

3. USER FEEDBACK ON THE RE-IMPLEMENTED SEIS8S

To assess the effectiveness of Seis8s’ new syntax and interface, I conducted both workshop-based testing and live performance trials. These contexts provided valuable opportunities to observe how musicians and audiences responded in practice—whether through hands-on exploration of the language, or through engagement with the system in a performance setting. Feedback was gathered informally, emphasizing participants’ impressions of usability, expressiveness, and visual impact.

The symbolic syntax was first tested in an online pilot workshop with approximately 15 participants during the *Transferencias Aurales II Encuentro Latinoamericano de Música y Tecnología* in Mexico City (November 11–15, 2024). The group included a mix of musicians and a few coders, most of whom were familiar with cumbia rhythms, as they were based in Mexico.

Information on participants’ experiences was collected through informal comments during workshop activities. While one participant found the earlier list-based syntax simpler, the overall response affirmed that the expressive visual system helped foster creative engagement. Participants also described the redesigned user interface as “exciting” and “friendly,” even for those unfamiliar with the underlying code.

The interface has also been tested in a full performance setting at the closing event of the *Expanded Data Conference* in Hamilton, Ontario, Canada (July 27, 2025). During this 16-minute performance, audience members engaged by dancing and even forming a conga line. Afterwards, several attendees commented informally that the interface offered “a lot to look at,” suggesting that it was visually engaging even for those without knowledge of live coding or music technology. This performance is available here: <https://youtu.be/ntYm0ae3sCY>.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The reimplementaion of Seis8s represents both a techni-

Figure 9: A Seis8s performance by the author during the Expanded Data Conference (Hamilton, July 2025).

cal evolution and a deepening of its cultural mission. By migrating from a Haskell-based architecture to a JavaScript ecosystem centered on Vue.js, Tone.js, and Tonal.js, this project has transformed from a proof-of-concept into a more accessible and expressive platform for Latin electronic music creation. The elimination of compilation delays and the adoption of widely-supported web technologies has fundamentally improved the development experience while maintaining the system’s core commitment to Spanish-language live coding.

The introduction of unified symbolic timelines marks a significant advancement in musical expressiveness, allowing performers to write rhythmically and melodically coherent phrases within a single notation system. This approach, informed by real-world practices such as jazz lead sheets and the Nashville Number System, bridges the gap between traditional musical literacy and computational creativity.

The visual redesign inspired by Peruvian Chicha aesthetics challenges conventional assumptions about interface design in creative coding environments. By embracing the vibrant, chaotic energy of street-level visual culture rather than conforming to corporate design systems, Seis8s positions itself as a form of cultural resistance within digital creative tools.

Overall, this work contributes to a growing body of research on culturally-situated creative coding platforms, demonstrating that technical systems are never culturally neutral. By grounding computational creativity in specific musical, linguistic, and visual traditions, Seis8s offers an alternative model for digital music tools, one that celebrates cultural specificity rather than pursuing false universality.

The technical innovations presented here, particularly the custom Peggy.js grammar for parsing symbolic timelines and the SVG-based interface approach, offer replicable strategies for other culturally-situated programming platforms. Furthermore, this reimplementaion suggests that there is both technical feasibility and community interest in creative coding environments that foreground non-dominant cultural perspectives.

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